

Small-scale linear Fresnel collector using air as heat transfer fluid: experimental characterization

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Abstract

Linear Fresnel collectors offer great potential for producing solar heat for industrial processes, both on a small and large scale. Thermal oil, pressurized water, or steam are used as heat transfer fluid in most applications, due to their suitable thermal properties. A heat exchanger is required for thermal power delivery to the user unless the heat transfer fluid is directly used as a medium in the industrial process. For those industrial applications using hot air as a process fluid, direct air heating inside linear Fresnel collectors can be an interesting solution aiming at simplification, cost reduction, and environmental and safety benefits.

In this experimental study, air is heated inside a commercial small-scale Linear Fresnel collector row of 79.2 m² active surface, demonstrating the viability of direct air heating up to 500 °C at its outlet. A commercial turbocharger pressurizes the air and reduces the blowing power. The purposely designed test campaign carried out in Madrid (Spain) during spring and summer seasons allowed the experimental contrast of a detailed 1D opto-thermal numerical model. Both static and purposely developed dynamic models of the receiver tube have been scrutinized and tested. The models and the experimental information allowed for the accurate characterization of both thermal losses and optical efficiency.

Keywords: Solar Air Heater; Linear Fresnel Collector; Solar Heat for Industrial Processes; Optical Performance; Receiver thermal model; Solar Drying.

Highlights

- Air is directly heated inside a commercial small-scale linear Fresnel collector.
- Air temperature up to 500 °C is reached without receiver tube damage.
- A dynamic 1D model is developed and experimentally verified.
- The optical collector efficiency is experimentally estimated.
- The solar tracking accuracy is characterized indicating specific improvements.

1 Introduction

Linear concentrating devices such as Parabolic Trough Collectors PTCs as well as Linear Fresnel Collectors LFCs are getting increasing attention for their capability of providing heat at higher temperatures than other collector types (Flat Plate Collector FPC, Evacuated Tube Collector ETC, or Air Collector AC), opening the

possibility of replacing fossil fuel for producing medium temperature Solar Heat for Industrial Processes SHIP. Several existing applications of LFC and PTC for SHIP were reviewed by [1] as well as by the SHIP database [2]. These applications use liquids, such as thermal oil, pressurized water, or even steam, as heat transfer fluid HTF.

Alternative gaseous HTFs in PTC have been investigated for application in solar Brayton cycles aiming at power generation, as in [3] and [4], among others. The use of compressed gaseous HTF in PTC has been analyzed in [5], including air, nitrogen, carbon dioxide, helium, and argon. Pressurized gaseous HTFs allow a wider range of operating temperatures compared to liquids, besides offering low cost and less environmental impact. As for drawbacks, they offer lower internal heat transfer coefficients and require high pumping power [6]. Air as HTF delivered at 500 °C has been experimentally investigated by [7] at atmospheric pressure, using an unconventional proprietary collector design.

Using air as HTF inside LFCs or PTCs is especially interesting for those SHIP applications requiring hot air as the process fluid in the low and medium temperature range ($T < 400$ °C). Industrial drying or dehydration is one of the high-energy demanding processes requiring hot air as heating and moisture carrying medium, applied to different materials and products (food, biomass, residues, moist sludge, minerals), as reported by [8] and [9]. Further potential applications include seawater desalination [10], paint curing [11], and indirect evaporative cooling [12], among others.

Direct solar air heating inside concentrating collectors opens the possibility of lower installation and maintenance costs, avoiding the heat exchanger and a costly primary liquid HTF, besides eliminating the related complexity of dilatation, bubbles, freezing, and the environmental risks of leakages, and disposal. This way, an open-to-atmosphere OA circuit layout can be implemented, similarly to current practice in non-concentrating Solar Air Heaters SAH that rarely heat above 100 °C.

Famiglietti [13] addresses the topic from a theoretical point of view. It analyzes the direct solar air heating inside concentrating collectors for industrial applications. The authors found it is feasible, and they pointed out two main important aspects to take into account. For one side, the risk of solar receiver overheating arises due to low wall to air heat transfer, when highly concentrated solar irradiance and low mass flow rate concur. On the other hand, the required blowing power grows with both collector row length and concentrated solar irradiance. This is a consequence of needing to increase the mass flow rate to limit both receiver wall temperature and outlet temperature. In the same study, they proposed a solution. It consists of implementing a null power efficiency Brayton cycle, coupling the solar field with a freewheeling automotive turbocharger to avoid the need for auxiliary energy consumption for pumping. This way a higher than atmospheric pressure operates inside the tubular receiver of an OA Turbo Solar Air Heater system (T-SAH). Moreover, the authors addressed the possibility of atmospheric pressure operation under some operating conditions. Direct air heating in a 633.6 m² solar field of Linear Fresnel collectors assisted by a turbocharger has been investigated numerically by [14]. Using accurate modeling of off-the-shelf collectors and a turbocharger, they obtained the T-SAH performance over representative days and the typical year in Madrid (Spain).

In the present work, an experimental investigation on a demonstrating plant of a T-SAH using a well-instrumented small-scale LFC is carried out. It aims to experimentally demonstrate the viability of using commercial LFCs with commercial evacuated tubes as receivers for medium temperatures direct hot air production. This information is currently non-available. For that, some results from the T-SAH are included. In addition, purposely designed experiments are devised for the full characterization of this innovative solar concept. 1D optical and thermal numerical models of the LFCs row and receiver tube have been implemented, validated, and tuned on experimental quasi-steady-state as well as transient operational data.

Receiver static thermal model has been implemented using well-known methodologies based on collector efficiency factor F' and heat removal factor F_R [26], besides applying spatial discretization for increasing the accuracy. A dynamic model has been obtained modifying F' and F_R for including receiver thermal inertia, aiming at better accuracy against transient data with low computation cost. Once validated, a dynamic receiver model has been used to obtain experimental optical efficiency on transient operational data. The comparison of experimental efficiency with optical model allowed to define an optical correction factor, accounting for optical errors and manufacturing imperfections, besides the sun tracking procedure accuracy. This innovative methodology could be applied to fully characterize similar solar air thermal systems.

2 Experimental setup

The experimental setup, depicted in Fig. 1, is installed at the Carlos III University of Madrid Campus, located in the city of Leganés (Spain). Three prototypal LFCs manufactured by [15] are installed in series, whose main features are reported in Table 1. The primary reflector is made of n_m mirrors having a linear parabolic shape to increase the optical efficiency, with an individual lateral aperture w_m , thus an overall aperture $W_a = n_m w_m$ and length L_m , Fig. 2. The secondary reflector is trapezoidal-shaped aiming to refocus on the receiver tube the imperfectly focused sun rays, Fig. 2, and to homogenize the circumferential distribution of irradiance impacting on the receiver tube. The three LFCs modules form a straight row with 79.2 m² overall capturing surface, whose axis forms an angle with the south direction of $\gamma_r = 54.3$ deg W on the horizontal plane. The tracking system uses motorized individual mirrors according to an astronomical algorithm, applied sequentially to each of them, checking each orientation with individual solid-state inclinometers. The collector is equipped with five evacuated receiver tubes with a selective coating, coming from the thermal-solar power plant sector, each one having an active length L_t . They were manufactured for using oil as HTF (HCEOI-12 Archimede Solar Energy [16]), having an external diameter $D_{ex} = 70$ mm, a maximum allowable wall temperature of 600 °C and a maximum operating temperature of 580 °C, Table 2.

The junction length separating two consecutive tubes, including the tube bellows, is $2L_j$ so that the total receiver length is $L_r = n_t(L_t + 2L_j)$. Stainless steel tube junctions were soldered to receiver extremities to allow pressure and temperature sensors installation, besides soldering flanges for easy receiver tube removal and inspection. The receiver thermal longitudinal dilatation expected due to temperature rise is not negligible for what a sliding system was installed to hang the tubes to the LFC structure avoiding mechanical stress and compression buckling. The dilatation of the receiver with respect to the glass cover evacuated tube is compensated by bellows according to the manufacturer's design, Fig. 3.

A joint blowing unit was implemented to pump ambient air throughout the receiver and to slightly increase the internal pressure by an auxiliary electrical blower ac (which can be bypassed) in series with a turbocompressor c , Fig. 1. Meanwhile, the power for the turbocompressor is recovered by a downstream turbine e , according to the layout proposed by [13]. Turbocompressor and turbine share a shaft as they come from a commercial automotive turbocharger. In the present setup, the model GT1544 by Garrett [17] was installed.

Class A type K thermocouple probes have been used, which were calibrated inside a stirred stabilized bath against a reference thermocouple, yielding a total uncertainty of ± 1.2 °C. The total measurement uncertainty considering installation errors has been estimated as ± 2.0 °C for the worst case. The mass flow rate is obtained from volume flow measurement at the atmospheric inlet by an airflow sensor (Schmidt 30.015 MPM) with a declared standard uncertainty of $\pm 3\%$. Absolute pressure measurements contribute with a nominal uncertainty of ± 25 mbar. Global solar irradiance G_{glo} on the horizontal plane and diffuse irradiance G_d have been measured using two pyranometers (Kipp&Zonen) with $\pm 3\%$ total uncertainty, and a shadow band. A 95% probability confidence interval has been used. Measured values were monitored continuously

and recorded with a time interval of $\Delta\tau = 30$ s by a SCADA, using a Programmable Logic Controller PLC (Unitronic USP-104-B10). When possible, averaging has been used to reduce random errors.

Figure 1. Experimental setup scheme of three modules and five receiver tubes highlighting the pressurizing turbocharger and the joint blowing unit.

Figure 2. Cross-section of the LFC primary and secondary reflectors.

Figure 3. Receiver tubes junction scheme, allowing thermal dilatation axial displacements.

Figure 4. Experimental installation at Carlos III University of Madrid, Leganés (Spain).

Table 1. LFC module and row.

Active module length	L_m	5.28 m
Aperture width	W_a	5.00 m
Height receiver	H_m	2.72 m
Active module area	A_m	26.40 m ²
Active row area	A_{tot}	79.2 m ²
Normal optical efficiency	η_{op0}	0.632
Mirrors per module	n_m	10
Mirror aperture width	w_m	0.50 m
Extra length	L_{ex1}	1.05 m
Extra length	L_{ex2}	1.02 m
Extra length	L_{ex3}	1.02 m
Extra length	L_{ex4}	1.52 m
Orientation (0 = South)	γ_r	54.3 deg W
Latitude	Φ_{loc}	40.165 deg N
Longitude	λ_{loc}	3.704 deg W

Table 2. Receiver tube details.

Active single tube length	L_t	3.902 m
Junction length	L_j	0.115 m
Number of tubes	n_t	5
Total receiver length	L_r	20.65 m
External diameter	D_{ex}	0.07 m
Tube wall thickness	e_t	0.002 m
Glass cover external diameter	$D_{g,ex}$	0.125 m
Glass cover thickness	e_g	0.003 m
Junction emissivity	ε_j	0.38

3 Numerical model

3.1 Linear Fresnel Collector

An optical model of a LFC is needed to predict the incident heat flux on the receiver resulting from the incidence direct normal solar irradiance G_{bn} impacting on the aperture the W_a . Assuming a uniform circumferential distribution on the receiver perimeter P_{ex} , a concentrated solar heat flux \dot{q}_s , Eq. (1), impacts the illuminated receiver length.

$$\dot{q}_s = \eta_{op} G_{bn} \frac{W_a}{P_{ex}} \quad (1)$$

The optical efficiency η_{op} can be expressed in terms of a normal optical efficiency η_{op0} , corresponding to null solar incidence angle $\theta_z = 0$ deg. The incidence angle modifiers *IAMs*, account for the efficiency variation with the transversal θ_T and longitudinal θ_L component of θ_z with respect to the LFC, according to Fig. 5.

$$\eta_{op} = \eta_{op0} IAM \cong \eta_{op0} IAM_T(\theta_T) IAM_L(\theta_L) \quad (2)$$

The angles θ_T and θ_L can be obtained from the collector azimuth angle γ_r and the sun position, i.e. sun azimuth γ_s and elevation α_s angles [18], and [19], Eqs. (3) to (4).

$$\theta_L = \sin^{-1} \left[\cos(\gamma_s - \gamma_r) \sin \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \alpha_s \right) \right] \quad (3)$$

$$\theta_T = \tan^{-1} \left[|\sin(\gamma_s - \gamma_r)| \tan \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \alpha_s \right) \right] \quad (4)$$

The manufacturer provided the incidence angle modifier $IAM_T(\theta_T)$ and $IAM_L(\theta_L)$ obtained by the raytracing technique, Fig.6. Since manufacturer's IAM_L included the length-dependent optical end losses effect, it has been replaced with $IAM_L(\theta_L) = \cos(\theta_L)$ to consider cosine effect only, Fig.6.

Figure 5. LFC solar incidence angles.

Figure 6. IAM_T and IAM_L for the LFC.

The module mirror fields are not continuous due to a maintenance spacing between consecutive collectors L_{ex2} and L_{ex3} so that the irradiation of the receiver is broken by non-illuminated intervals of the same length, Fig. 7. In addition, the non-illuminated length can appear at one receiver extremity, while the opposite end can be fully or partially illuminated, according to longitudinal angle θ_L . Part of concentrated irradiance impacts out of the receiver for large θ_L , when $z_3 + L_t > L_r$, which is referred to as optical end loss. The distribution of \dot{q}_s along the tube length depends on the longitudinal incidence angle θ_L , the geometry of the collector row and receiver height, according to Fig. 7 and Eqs. (5) and (6).

Figure 7. Longitudinal view collector row of three modules.

$$\dot{q}_s(z) = \begin{cases} \dot{q}_s & \text{for } z_k < z < z_k + L_m; k = 1, 2, 3 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} z_1 &= L_{ex1} + \bar{H}_m \tan \theta_L \\ z_2 &= z_1 + L_m + L_{ex2} \\ z_3 &= z_2 + L_m + L_{ex3} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

An average distance from the tube to the reflector can be defined \bar{H}_m [19]:

$$\bar{H}_m = \sqrt{(W_a/4)^2 + H_m^2} \quad (7)$$

Figure 8. Effect of collectors spacing L_{ex} on the receiver irradiation.

3.2 Receiver

Thermal modeling of an evacuated receiver tube was presented by several authors following different approaches, either for application to PTCs, [20], [21], [22] and LFCs, [23], [24], among others. Common techniques are reviewed by [25], including one-dimensional (1D) and three-dimensional approaches, either static or dynamic.

A 1D model is implemented here, since homogenous concentrated solar heat flux allows to consider a unique receiver wall temperature at each cross-section, neglecting circumferential temperature gradients, either for static and dynamic formulation. While a static model is suitable for general prediction and design, a dynamic model can better fit the experimental results under the actual sun, for purposely designed transient tests, and optical efficiency experimental estimation.

3.2.1 Static model

The steady-state methodology recommended by [26] is used for computing the useful heat power \dot{Q}_u transferred to the air flow along a certain irradiated receiver length L^* . That approach relies on length-constant external and internal heat coefficients, U_L and h_a , constant heat flux \dot{q}_s , and fluid properties, along the considered receiver length L^* , with t indicating stagnation properties, Eq. (8). This configures a canonical model, widely accepted.

$$\dot{Q}_u = F_R L^* P_{ex} [\dot{q}_s - U_L (T_{in} - T_{amb})] = \dot{m} (c_{p,ou} T_{ou,t} - c_{p,in} T_{in,t}) \quad (8)$$

Eq. (9) gives the collector efficiency factor F' , here including the extra feature of $P_{ex} > P$. The heat removal factor F_R is obtained integrating the temperature from the tube inlet $z = 0$ where $T = T_{in}$ to the outlet $z = L^*$ where $T = T_{ou}$, Eq. (10).

$$F' = \frac{\dot{q}_s - U_L (T_w - T_{amb})}{\dot{q}_s - U_L (T - T_{amb})} = \frac{\dot{q}_s - U_L (T_w - T_{amb})}{\dot{q}_s - U_L (T_w - T_{amb}) + U_L \Delta T_w} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{U_L \Delta T_w}{\dot{q}_s - U_L (T_w - T_{amb})}} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{U_L P_{ex}}{h_a P}} \quad (9)$$

$$F' P_{ex} dz = \frac{\dot{m} c_p dT_t}{\dot{q}_s - U_L (T - T_{amb})} \Rightarrow F_R = \frac{\dot{m} c_p}{L^* P_{ex} U_L} \left[1 - \exp \left(- \frac{L^* F' P_{ex} U_L}{\dot{m} c_p} \right) \right] \quad (10)$$

Values of U_L , h_a and fluid properties are temperature-dependent variables and can be estimated at the inlet, knowing T_{in} . $T_{w,in}$ is estimated iteratively through Eq. (11). The Gnielinski correlation [27] allows estimating the internal heat transfer coefficient, Eq. (12).

$$\dot{q}_s - U_L (T_w - T_{amb}) = \dot{q}_u = \frac{h_a P (T_w - T)}{P_{ex}} \quad (11)$$

$$h_a = \frac{\frac{f}{8} (Re_D - 1000) Pr \frac{k_a}{D}}{1 + 12.7 \left(\frac{f}{8} \right)^{0.5} \left(Pr^{\frac{2}{3}} - 1 \right)}; \quad f = (1.82 \log Re_D - 1.64)^{-2}; \quad Re_D = \frac{4\dot{m}}{\mu \pi D} \quad (12)$$

The discretization of the tube length L_t into n_e elements allows an increased accuracy since the variable U_L , h_a , as well as the fluid properties, can be evaluated at the inlet of each element $\Delta L = L_t/n_e$. This is especially relevant for U_L which shows a noticeable dependency on wall temperature. On the other hand, the use of F' and F_R allows high accuracy using a small n_e , reducing the computational effort. It is worth mentioning that due to discontinuous distribution of heat flux along the receiver length, as from Eq. (5), $\dot{q}_s \langle z \rangle$ could results not constant in a given element length ΔL . For each element i the mean value of \dot{q}_s along ΔL can be used in Eq. (8), being $\bar{\dot{q}}_{s,i} = \Delta L^{-1} \int_{z_{e,i}}^{z_{e,i} + \Delta L} \dot{q}_s \langle z \rangle$ and $z_{e,i}$ the coordinate of the starting edge of element i .

Combined heat transfer from the external tube surface to ambient through the coaxial glass tube of the evacuated receiver is taken into account through a global heat transfer coefficient U_L . [20], among others, offer a physical model to predict U_L considering the numerous basic heat transfer mechanisms involved. Alternative and more convenient empirical expressions can be used. Here a polynomial expression for $U_L \langle T_w, T_{amb} \rangle$ is obtained from experimental thermal losses reported by [28] for a very similar evacuated tube receiver also having $D_{ex} = 0.070$ m, surrounded by an ambient temperature $T_{amb} = 23$ °C, Eq. (13). Coefficients are reported in Table 3. Fig. 9. depicts the resulting curve.

$$U_L \langle T_w, T_{amb} \rangle = c_{U3} (T_w - T_{amb})^3 + c_{U2} (T_w - T_{amb})^2 + c_{U1} (T_w - T_{amb}) + c_{U0} \quad (13)$$

Table 3. Coefficients of the U_L correlation in Eq. (13).

U_L coefficients		
c_{U0}	$-5.075 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$W m^{-2} K^{-1}$
c_{U1}	0.011	$W m^{-2} K^{-2}$
c_{U2}	$-3.076 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$W m^{-2} K^{-3}$
c_{U3}	$7.645 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$W m^{-2} K^{-4}$

Figure 9. Correlation for $U_L(T_w, T_{amb})$ fitting experimental data by [28], according to Eq. (13).

Thermal losses for the junction length l_j were estimated through a coefficient $U_{L,j}$. The irradiation losses coefficient is h_{ir} , Eq. (15). The convection losses coefficient h_{co} is estimated from an expression developed by Churchill and Chu [29] for no wind case, Eq. (16) involving the Rayleigh number Ra . The supporting bracket thermal losses coefficient h_{bra} is estimated following [20], Eq. (17), where A_{bra} is the minimum cross-section of the bracket, and P_{bra} is the bracket perimeter.

$$U_{L,j} = h_{ir} + h_{co} + h_{bra} \quad (14)$$

$$h_{ir} = \frac{\sigma \varepsilon_j (T_{w,j}^4 - T_{amb}^4)}{T_{w,j} - T_{amb}} \quad (15)$$

$$h_{co} = \left(0.60 + \frac{0.387 Ra^{1/6}}{\left[1 + \left(\frac{0.559}{Pr} \right)^{9/16} \right]^{8/27}} \right)^2 \frac{k_a}{D_{ex}} ; \quad Ra = \frac{g \left(\frac{T_w + T_{amb}}{2} \right)^{-1} (T_w - T_{amb}) D_{ex}^3}{\nu \alpha} \quad (16)$$

$$h_{bra} = \frac{\sqrt{h_{co}P_{bra}k_wA_{bra}}}{P_{ex}L_j} \quad (17)$$

3.2.2 Dynamic model

An original receiver tube dynamic model is developed, aiming at low computation cost and time, by modifying F' , from Eq. (9) and F_R from Eq. (10) to include the thermal inertia effect.

The energy balance within an infinitesimal time interval $d\tau$ on a receiver tube length dz can be formulated as in Eq. (18), being respectively C_w, A_w, ρ_w the thermal capacity, cross-section area, and density of the receiver tube. Assuming a finite-difference on time variable τ , with $d\tau \approx \Delta\tau$, it turns into Eq. (19).

$$dT\dot{m}c_p = P_{ex}\dot{q}_s dz - P_{ex}U_L(T_w - T_{amb})dz - C_w A_w \rho_w dz \frac{dT_w}{d\tau} \quad (18)$$

$$\frac{dT}{dz}\dot{m}c_p = P_{ex}\left(\dot{q}_s - U_L(T_w - T_{amb}) - \frac{C_w A_w \rho_w (T_w - T_w^{\tau-\Delta\tau})}{P_{ex} \Delta\tau}\right) \quad (19)$$

Defining an equivalent capacitive heat transfer coefficient $U_C = \frac{C_w A_w \rho_w}{P_{ex} \Delta\tau}$, F' can be reformulated as follows, Eq. (20).

$$F' = \frac{\dot{q}_s - U_L(T_w - T_{amb}) - U_C(T_w - T_w^{\tau-\Delta\tau})}{\dot{q}_s - U_L(T - T_{amb}) - U_C(T - T_w^{\tau-\Delta\tau})} = \frac{1}{1 + (U_L + U_C) \frac{P_{ex}}{h_a P}} \quad (20)$$

F' allows substituting T_w with air temperature T in Eq. (19), obtaining Eq. (21). Integrating over z , Eq. (22) and solving for $T = T_{ou}$ and $z = L^*$ results in Eq. (23).

$$\frac{dT}{dz}\dot{m}c_p = P F'_s [\dot{q}_s - U_L(T - T_{amb}) - U_C(T - T_w^{\tau-\Delta\tau})] \quad (21)$$

$$\frac{\dot{q}_s - U_L(T - T_{amb}) - U_C(T - T_w^{\tau-\Delta\tau})}{\dot{q}_s - U_L(T_{in} - T_{amb}) - U_C(T_{in} - T_w^{\tau-\Delta\tau})} = \exp\left(-\frac{z P_{ex}(U_L + U_C)}{\dot{m}c_p}\right) \quad (22)$$

$$\frac{\dot{q}_s - U_L(T_{ou} - T_{amb}) - U_C(T_{ou} - T_w^{\tau-\Delta\tau})}{\dot{q}_s - U_L(T_{in} - T_{amb}) - U_C(T_{in} - T_w^{\tau-\Delta\tau})} = \exp\left(-\frac{L^* P_{ex}(U_L + U_C)}{\dot{m}c_p}\right) \quad (23)$$

Introducing F_R , Eq. (24) gives the power gain by the air flow over a generic length L^* explicitly, Eq. (25).

$$F_R = \frac{\dot{m}c_p(T_{ou} - T_{in})}{L^* P_{ex} [\dot{q}_s - U_L(T_{in} - T_{amb}) - U_C(T_{in} - T_w^{\tau-\Delta\tau})]} = \frac{\dot{m}c_{p,m}}{P_{ex} L^* (U_L + U_C)} \left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{F' P_{ex}(U_L + U_C)L^*}{\dot{m}c_{p,m}}\right)\right] \quad (24)$$

$$\dot{Q}_u = F_R L^* P_{ex} [\dot{q}_s - U_L(T_{in} - T_{amb}) - U_C(T_{in} - T_w^{\tau-\Delta\tau})] = \dot{m}(c_{p,ou} T_{ou} - c_{p,in} T_{in}) \quad (25)$$

Eq. (25) allows calculating \dot{Q}_u over a generic length L^* ; actually, a discretized element length $\Delta L = L_t/n_e$ to increase the accuracy, as explained for the steady-state case. It is worth mentioning that here is assumed $U_L(T_w, T_{amb})$ according to Eq. (13), neglecting the thermal inertia of the cover glass tube. The time-finite difference is assumed to equal the SCADA acquisition time interval $\Delta\tau = 30$ s. For this time interval a value of $U_C \cong 260 \text{ W } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$ is found for the receiver tube.

The presented approach is extended to the junction length between the receiver tubes L_j using the corresponding $U_{C,j}$.

4 Results

4.1 Thermal losses model validation

A first specific test has been carried out on the receiver tube to validate the discretized receiver model, either the static or the dynamic one, devising a test with the partial shut-off of the concentrated irradiance. For this aim, only two of the downstream last tubes were considered for the validation, $L^* = L_L$, being permanently non-irradiated, as in Fig. 10 and Fig. 11, thus incorporating only heat losses in a transient test heating and cooling by the upstream tubes.

Figure 10. Thermal losses test layout.

Figure 11. Thermal losses test, the downstream receiver is partially irradiated.

Fig. 12 reports the experimental temperature T_{in} and T_{ou} , during the thermal losses test, respectively at the inlet and outlet of the tested receiver length L_L as in Fig. 10. T_{in} was progressively increased using solar energy gathered by the irradiated upstream three tubes, up to 380 °C. Then they were defocused to perform the cooling transient. The static and the dynamic model were applied to compute the outlet temperature, T_{ou}^{st} and T_{ou}^{dy} respectively, over the length L_L , using measured T_{in} as input, together with mass flow rate, air pressure, ambient temperature, and null \dot{q}_s .

Figure 12. Thermal losses test results. Temperatures at inlet and outlet of L_L .

T_{ou}^{st} diverges from T_{ou} during the transient heating and cooling, while is quite precise at the peak, 9.5 hr, when the time variation of T_{ou} is smoother and closer to steady-state conditions. As expected, the dynamic model can account for the receiver tube thermal inertia jointly with the correct thermal losses yielding a robust validation concerning the T_{ou}^{dy} values. As a result, the thermal losses account and the herewith proposed implementation of U_c seems correct, but still more features need validation.

4.2 Solar air heating

This section reports an experimental test of solar air heating during a clear summer typical day to demonstrate the viability of air heating inside the receiver of LFCs row. The three solar modules were in tracking mode during the considered time interval.

The irradiances, G_{glo} for global, and G_d for diffuse on horizontal surfaces were measured and used to determine the horizontal direct irradiance G_b , Fig. 13. Fig. 14(a) reports the inlet and outlet temperature vs. True Solar Time TST . Due to the low heat capacity of air, despite a relative short collector row, an outlet temperature T_{ou} above 400 °C is reached after a transient of ~ 1 hr. A peak temperature of 500 °C is reached at solar noon.

Absolute air pressure was higher than atmospheric, up to 1.4 bar, Fig. 14(b). This is due to the joint blowing unit which includes a turbocharger and an auxiliary electric blower, Fig. 1. Their performances are not analyzed in this work. The mass flow rate measured varied smoothly, as Fig. 14(b) shows.

Thermal dilatation of the receiver tube occurs during heating, reaching an overall length extension up to ≈ 150 mm, confirming the suitability of the sliding hanger system and the end flexible connections installed, Fig. 3. On the other hand, excessive receiver tube bending is recognized as a risk of glass cover breakage when the bending displacement of the tube makes it touch the cover glass tube. Tube bending seems due to non-uniform circumferential temperature, which originates a non-uniform peripheric wall dilatation, more substantial using air than using liquid HTF. Secondary reflectors are beneficial for distributing the solar heat flux across the receiver perimeter. In the present experiment, bending has been observed, especially during the starting transient when tubes still encompass circumferential temperature homogenization. Nevertheless, no damage to the cover glass occurred.

Figure 13. Solar irradiance measurements during the clear summer day.

(a)

(b)

Figure 14. Summer clear day results. (a) Air temperature. (b) Air mass flow rate, inlet, and outlet pressure.

4.3 Optical efficiency experimental quantification

The above-described experimental data of a typical summer day has been used to validate the collector and receiver model. The receiver tube model was solved either in the static or dynamic formulation, assuming the experimental inlet air conditions for each time step: T_{in} , p_{in} , mass flow rate \dot{m} , ambient conditions p_{amb} , T_{amb} , horizontal global irradiance G_{gl} and diffuse G_d . The sun position is calculated according to [26], as reported in the Appendix, yielding α_s , γ_s , and θ_z . The direct normal irradiance is obtained as $G_{bn} = (G_{gl} - G_d)/\cos\theta_z$. In Fig. 15(a), the solar incidence angle longitudinal component θ_L and transversal component θ_T come from Eqs. (3) and (4). The end losses factor was estimated as $f_{end} = (L_r - L_{irr,out})/L_r$, where $L_{irr,out}$ is the length of concentrated irradiance exceeding the receiver length from one or another extremity. Receiver extensions at the extremities L_{ex1} and L_{ex4} allow to increase the time interval with $f_{end} = 1$, thus with null end losses. Eq. (2) gives the incidence angle modifiers $IAMs$ in Fig. 6 and $\eta_{op0} = 0.632$ provided by the manufacturer. Fig. 15(b) depicts the expected optical efficiency η_{op} , as well as the concentrated heat flux \dot{q}_s . Since in this facility the initial focusing procedure is not instantaneous, a linear growth of \dot{q}_s from null non-tracking value to full tracking value was assumed during the focusing transient interval, which lasted approximately 6 min.

(a)

(b)

Figure 15. Collector model results. (a) LFC row solar angles, IAMs and f_{end} . (b) Concentrated heat flux and experimental optical efficiency.

Fig. 16(a) plots the outlet tube air temperatures, calculated through the static and dynamic models, respectively T_{ou}^{st} and T_{ou}^{dy} , with the corresponding measured air temperature T_{ou} . Fig. 16(b) plots the corresponding power to the airflow inside the receiver, \dot{Q}_u^{st} , \dot{Q}_u^{dy} , and the experimental data for $\dot{Q}_u = (T_{ou}cp_{ou} - T_{in}cp_{in})\dot{m}$.

(a)

(b)

Figure 16. Comparison of the model results using the manufacturer η_{op} with the experimental results. (a) Air outlet temperature. (b) Useful power to the air flow.

The results show that the model overestimates both the outlet temperature and power gain. The deviation increases after the peak power is reached. Further simulations confirmed that the results were not very sensitive to the heat loss coefficients or the thermal inertia, respectively U_L and U_C . Furthermore, the results were much more affected by the concentrated solar heat flux. This suggests that the actual optical collector efficiency can be lower than the value delivered by the manufacturer. This can be due to several imperfections affecting the real system, not properly accounted for by η_{op} , Eq.(2). Common optical errors in concentrating systems are reviewed in [30]. Imperfectly manufactured reflectors, deformations due to aging, tracking errors, reflectors displacement due to wind, among others, are potential causes of loss of optical efficiency. An empirical optical efficiency η_{op}^{exp} can be estimated from experimental performances and real sun data, using the dynamic receiver model for thermal losses estimation. At each time step η_{op}^{exp} is the optical efficiency that the collectors must hold to give at the collector outlet the same temperature T_{ou}^{dy} as the experimental value T_{ou} , thus giving a negligible deviation $|\dot{Q}_u^{dy} - \dot{Q}_u|$. An iterative calculation scheme allows to obtain η_{op}^{exp} satisfying Eq.(26) for each time step, where the thermal power to air of each receiver element $\dot{Q}_{u,i}^{dy}$ is obtained according to Eqs.(24) and (25), using a concentrating heat flux $\dot{q}_s = \eta_{op}^{exp} G_{bn} W_a P_{ex}^{-1}$ in Eq.(5).

$$\dot{Q}_u^{dy} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_e} \dot{Q}_{u,i}^{dy} = \dot{m}(c_{p,ou}T_{ou} - c_{p,in}T_{in}) \quad (26)$$

Fig. 17(a) shows that η_{op}^{exp} is lower than the expected theoretical $\eta_{op} = \eta_{op0} IAM_T \langle \theta_T \rangle IAM_L \langle \theta_L \rangle$, so that an empirical efficiency correction term η_{cor} can be defined and evaluated, Eq. (27).

$$\eta_{cor} = \frac{\eta_{op}^{exp}}{\eta_{op}} \quad (27)$$

As reported in Fig. 17(a), $\eta_{cor} < 1$ was found. Its value varied across a mean value during the first hours of experimentation and started to drop in the afternoon hours. This suggests exploring the relationship between the correction efficiency η_{cor} and operating parameters.

A clear dependence of η_{cor} on solar angles θ_T or θ_L has not been observed; instead, a drop with $d\theta_T/d\tau$ was found. This suggests that a tracking error arises when $d\theta_T/d\tau$ increases, due to loss of focus within the interval of time separating two consecutive tracking angle adjustments. Tracking error in concentrating systems, including LFC applications, has been studied by several authors [31], [32], [33], among others. They point out that power loss increases with tracking angle deviation according to the geometry of the concentrator. Due to the large focal distance, LFCs are very sensitive to tracking accuracy, for which they need a precise tracking system as well as secondary optics to recover part of concentrated irradiance missing the receiver tube. Among other causes, it is well known that time lag between consecutive tracking angle adjustment can induce a focusing error. In the present setup, the tracking system checks continuously one by one the mirrors of a module, taking approximately 20 s for each of the 10 mirrors. Each mirror is refocused any $\tau_{tr} \approx 200$ s so that the tracking error due to lag between two consecutive adjustments is $\sigma_{tr} = (d\theta_T/d\tau)\tau_{tr}$. At each instant, each mirror has a different tracking error, being theoretically null for the last checked mirror and growing to σ_{tr} for the next one in the checking loop routine. η_{cor} is plotted against σ_{tr} in Fig. 17(b). It can be noticed that from a certain angle deviation σ_{tr} the effect of tracking lag is remarkable over other possible errors. A reasonable assumption is considering $\eta_{cor} = \eta_{st}\eta_{tr}$ where a static term η_{st} accounts for static imperfections (mirrors and receiver cleanness, manufacturing errors, bending, slope,

imperfect reflectivity) and a term η_{tr} accounts for the tracking lag error. As a threshold for η_{tr} to take place noticeably, $\sigma_{tr}^* = 7$ mrad can be assumed according to Fig. 17(b). For $\sigma_{tr} < \sigma_{tr}^*$ the tracking error effect is neglected and $\eta_{tr} = 1$, so that $\eta_{cor} = \eta_{st}$. An average value of $\bar{\eta}_{st} = 0.69$ was found for $\sigma_{tr} < \sigma_{tr}^*$.

For $\sigma_{tr} > \sigma_{tr}^*$ part of reflected irradiance is supposed to go out of the receiver diameter during a certain portion of the tracking time interval τ_{tr} . Although the trapezoidal secondary reflector can recover part of the irradiance missing the receiver tube, an optical efficiency drop is reasonably expected and accounted for by $\eta_{tr} = \eta_{cor}/\bar{\eta}_{st}$, which Fig. 17(b) shows. In fact, among the available non-imaging secondary optics, the trapezoidal shape offers lower performances compared to adaptative geometries, CPC, or segmented parabolic-shaped secondary optics [34], [35] among others.

Figure 17. Empirical correction for optical efficiency. (a) Experimental and theoretical optical efficiencies, η_{op}^{exp} and η_{op} respectively. (b) η_{cor} and η_{tr} versus σ_{tr} .

For the range of σ_{tr} corresponding to the present dataset, the tracking efficiency can be approximated as a linear function of σ_{tr} as follows, with $c_{tr} = -40.9 \text{ rad}^{-1}$

$$\eta_{tr}(\sigma_{tr}) = 1 - c_{tr}(\sigma_{tr} - \sigma_{tr}^*) \quad (28)$$

$$\eta_{cor}(\sigma_{tr}) = \eta_{tr}(\sigma_{tr}) \cdot \bar{\eta}_{st} \quad (29)$$

The modeled correction for optical efficiency, Eq. (29), can be used for running the dynamic and static models to verify their effect on the main outputs T_{ou} and \dot{Q}_u . For that, $\eta_{op,cor} = \eta_{op0}IAM_TIAM_L\eta_{cor}(\sigma_{tr})$ was used instead of $\eta_{op} = \eta_{op0}IAM_TIAM_L$ delivering good results, as reported in Fig. 18, with an RMS deviation of 10 °C on T_{ou} and 450 W on \dot{Q}_{ou} for the dynamic model and 48 °C on T_{ou} and 1760 W on \dot{Q}_{ou} for the less accurate static model.

Figure 18. Validation of the corrected optical efficiency. (a) Dynamic model. (b) Static model.

The calculation for η_{tr} and the estimation of η_{st} was repeated for another experimental test obtained on a typical spring day. Despite the slightly different testing conditions (mirrors tracking calibration, mirrors and receiver cleanness, wind, etc.) $\bar{\eta}_{st} = 0.72$ was found, close to the previous summer value. η_{tr} had similar trend of previous summer case, confirming the validity of the assumption made. Besides, due to the larger test duration along the day, higher angles σ_{tr} were reached during the test, comparing with the previous summer one, and the effect of tracking angle error can be observed over a larger range. For larger σ_{tr} , η_{tr} is still dropping with σ_{tr} but at a lower rate. For small σ_{tr} a linear approximation seems acceptable. A better approximation over a larger σ_{tr} range was obtained using a potential function as follows, with $c_{tr1} = 1.754 \text{ rad}^{-1}$ and $c_{tr2} = 0.488$, Eq. (30), Fig. 19.

$$\eta_{tr}(\sigma_{tr}) = 1 - c_{tr1}(\sigma_{tr} - \sigma_{tr}^*)^{c_{tr2}} \quad (30)$$

Figure 19. Empirical corrections for optical efficiency (spring clear day). (a) Experimental and theoretical optical efficiencies, η_{op}^{exp} and η_{op} respectively. (b) η_{cor} and η_{tr} versus σ_{tr} .

The static and the dynamic model were solved using $\eta_{op,cor} = \eta_{op0} IAM_T IAM_L \eta_{cor}(\sigma_{tr})$ with the potential approximation for $\eta_{cor}(\sigma_{tr})$. The results show a low RMS deviation of 32 °C on T_{ou} and 1210 W on \dot{Q}_{ou} for the static model and 5 °C on T_{ou} and 250 W on \dot{Q}_{ou} for the dynamic model, a substantial improvement. Fig. 20 shows the high coherence with experimental data obtained for the time evolution.

Figure 20. Validation of the corrected optical efficiency for a spring day test. (a) Dynamic model. (b) Static model.

Although a complete optical efficiency characterization requires a deep analysis of errors, supported by raytracing techniques and extended measurement and testing campaigns, besides needing a higher level of measurement techniques, the limited experimental analysis carried out allows improving the predictions by the numerical model for the specific collector used in the facility under study at a reasonable expenditure of time and cost. This kind of experimental quantification could be part of the commissioning process of more conventional facilities.

Even though the dynamic model is required to predict rapid transients, the static model can give acceptable results during quasi-steady operation, such as on the central hours of the day.

4.4 Receiver thermal features

Additional features can be observed solving the model at the power peak of the tested summer day. Fig. 21(a) plots the air temperature profile along the tube length $T_{ou,i}^{cal}$ calculated from the dynamic model and corrected optical efficiency $\eta_{op,cor}$, allowing a comparison with the measured air temperature at each tube outlet T_{ou}^{exp} , showing good agreement. A low discretization element number $n_e = 10$ has been used. The wall temperature T_w is also depicted. It increased along z despite the discontinuity induced by the junctions between tubes.

As expected, due to low internal heat transfer, the overtemperature $\Delta T_w = T_w - T_a$ is remarkable on the irradiated tube length. ΔT_w is ≈ 200 °C at the tube entrance and decreases down to ~ 50 °C toward the outlet. This is coherent with Eq. (11): for a given \dot{q}_s , the increase of T_w consequent to higher T , translates into higher U_L and lower $\dot{q}_u = \dot{q}_s - U_L(T_w - T_{amb})$, hence lower $\Delta T_w = \dot{q}_u P_{ex} / (h_a P)$, being h_a mainly dependent on the Reynolds number. The drop in \dot{q}_u with z can be observed in Fig. 21(b). The receiver tube thermal limit of 600 °C is not overcome, avoiding the receiver damage. Fig. 21(a) plots the variation of U_L , showing an increase with T_w up to a value of $10 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$ for the receiver tube, while for uncovered stainless steel junction elements between two tubes increased up to $U_{L,j} \approx 20 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$. This indicates the necessity of reducing this parameter and/or the reduction of the extension length.

Fig. 21(b) plots the concentrated heat flux on the receiver $\dot{q}_s = \eta_{op,cor} G_{bn} W_a P_{ex}^{-1}$. Its distribution on the receiver length $\dot{q}_s(z)$, according to Eq. (5), can be observed as well as its discretized approximation $\bar{q}_{s,i}$, constant along each discretization element i . Heat flux to ambient $\dot{q}_s - \dot{q}_u = U_L(T_w - T_{amb})$ increased with wall temperature T_w . Non-irradiated length due to spacing between LFCs and end effect can both be observed. Fig. 21 shows the detailed information that can be obtained from the models herewith proposed. Among other issues, they quantify the improvements possible by reducing the important losses in tube junctions and additional spacing, L_{ex2} , L_{ex3} and the increased L_j .

(a)

(b)

Figure 21. Receiver thermal distributions at power peak. (a). Air and receiver wall temperatures and heat losses coefficient. (b) Concentrated heat fluxes.

5 Conclusions

Experimental investigations on the innovative direct air heating inside a nearly NE-SW-oriented small-scale Linear Fresnel collector demonstrating facility has been carried out in this work, showing its viability.

During a typical clear summer day in Madrid (Spain) air temperature at the receiver tube outlet up to 500 °C has been reached without overcoming the receiver wall temperature limit. Although tube bending has been observed, no cover tube damage has been detected.

The results demonstrate the feasibility of the direct air heating inside the evacuated tube in a Linear Fresnel collector with modest air pressure, which was less than 1.5 bar, here provided by a turbocharger. Moreover, the results encourage further investigation of direct air heating even at atmospheric pressure, including the use of Parabolic Trough Collectors.

Owing to the short length of the solar field and its unavoidable orientation because of the allowable roof space, optical end losses were high during the early morning and afternoon hours. Receiver extensions at its extremities L_{ex1} and L_{ex2} allow a longer time interval of null end losses. Inter-module access space L_{ex2} and L_{ex3} for maintenance and the increased L_j contribute to lowering the efficiency of the receiver by increasing thermal losses.

1D static and dynamic numerical models for the receiver tube have been implemented and validated on the performed tests. The discretized receiver model takes into account the non-continuous solar field, as well as the junction elements connecting consecutive receiver tubes.

The receiver tube static model has been improved in a straightforward way incorporating a thermal inertia coefficient U_C complementing the overall heat losses coefficient U_L , by modifying the efficiency and heat removal factors, F' and F_R respectively.

The purposely designed transient heating and cooling tests with partial solar irradiance allowed validating the dynamic model. Its use seems unavoidable for high accuracy, owing to the low heat capacity of air in comparison to tube thermal inertia. The experimental data obtained corroborate this assumption.

The solar power gain was lower than expected from the specifications due to transient tracking errors besides manufacturing imperfections. The theoretical optical efficiency obtained using the given IAMs and the normal incidence optical efficiency η_{op0} did not provide accurate results, especially when the tracking angle has to change fast. Of especial importance is a tracking error that arises between the serial alignment of each mirror that takes a long time. Using experimental data and the dynamic model an experimental optical efficiency has been estimated allowing the definition of a correction term for the optical efficiency. Correction term takes into account both static errors and tracking errors. As a result, the model can anticipate accurately instantaneous performances and underpin improvements to the solar collector understudy and similar ones.

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7 Nomenclature

Latin

A_{bra}	Minimum cross section bracket [m ²]
B	Parameter equation of time [rad]
c_p	Air constant p specific heat capacity [J kg ⁻¹ °C ⁻¹]
c_{tr}, c_{tr1}	Coefficient tracking efficiency [rad ⁻¹]
c_{tr2}	Coefficient tracking efficiency [-]
$c_{U,i}$	Coefficient for polynomial fitting of U_L [W m ⁻² k ⁻⁵⁺ⁱ]

D	Inner diameter of the receiver tube [m]
D_g	Glass cover internal diameter [m]
E	Correction equation of time [s]
e_t	Tube thickness [m]
e_g	Glass cover thickness [m]
F'	Collector efficiency factor [-]
F_R	Collector heat removal factor [-]
F_m	Focal distance [m]
f	Darcy friction factor [-]
f_{end}	Optical end losses factor [-]
g	Gravitational acceleration [m s^{-2}]
G_{bn}	Normal beam irradiance [W m^{-2}]
G_d	Diffuse irradiance [W m^{-2}]
G_{glo}	Global irradiance on horizontal surface [W m^{-2}]
h_a	Air heat transfer coefficient [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$]
h_{ir}	Radiation heat transfer coefficient [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$]
h_{co}	Convection heat transfer coefficient [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$]
h_{bra}	Bracket heat transfer coefficient [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$]
H_m	Receiver distance from reflectors plane [m]
IAM	Incidence angle modifier [-]
k	Thermal conductivity [$\text{W m}^{-1} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$]
L^*	Receiver generic length [m]
L_{exi}	Extra lengths [m]
L_j	Junction length [m]
L_m	LFC length [m]
L_L	Thermal losses test length [m]
L_r	Receiver overall length [m]
LST	Local standard time [hr]
\dot{m}	Air mass flow rate [kg s^{-1}]
n_d	Day of the year
n_e	Number of elements in one tube [-]

n_m	Number of mirrors [-]
n_t	Number of tubes [-]
P	Receiver tube cross-section perimeter [m]
P_{bra}	Bracket perimeter [m]
Pr	Prandtl number [-]
p	Pressure [Pa]
\dot{Q}	Thermal power [W]
Q	Thermal energy [J]
\dot{q}_s	Incident concentrated solar irradiance [W m^{-2}]
\dot{q}_u	Thermal power flux to air [W m^{-2}]
Re	Reynolds number [-]
Ra	Rayleigh number [-]
T	Temperature [K, °C]
TST	True solar time [hr]
U_C	Capacitive equivalent heat transfer coefficient [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1}$]
U_L	Thermal losses coefficient [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1}$]
UTC	Standard time zone of Universal Coordinate Time [s]
W_a	Aperture total width [m]
w_m	Aperture width of a single reflector of LFC [m]
W_r	Width of concentrated irradiance [m]
z	Longitudinal coordinate for receiver [m]

Greek

α_s	Solar elevation [rad]
α_{abs}	Solar absorptance [-]
γ_s	Solar azimuth [rad]
γ_r	LFC azimuth [rad]
δ	Sun declination [rad]
ε	Emissivity [-]
η_{op0}	Normal optical efficiency [-]
η_{cor}	Correction efficiency [-]
η_{op}	Optical efficiency [-]

η_{st}	Static correction for efficiency [-]
η_{tr}	Tracking efficiency [-]
λ_{st}	Local time zone standard meridian longitude west [deg]
λ_{loc}	Collector location longitude west [deg]
μ	Dynamic viscosity [$\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$]
ν	Kinematic viscosity [$\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$]
Φ_{loc}	Latitude north [deg]
ρ	Density [kg m^{-3}]
σ	Stefan-Boltzmann constant [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-4}$]
σ_{tr}	Tracking error [rad]
σ_{tr}^*	Tracking error threshold [rad]
θ_L	Longitudinal angle [rad]
θ_s	Half-angle of solar beam cone [rad]
θ_T	Transversal angle [rad]
θ_z	Solar zenith angle [rad]
τ	Time [s]
ω_s	Hour angle [rad] (negative in the morning)

Subscripts

a	Air
amb	Ambient
cor	Correction
d	Direct
ex	External, extra
g	Glass cover
i	Discretization element
in	Inlet
j	Tube junction
m	LFC module, mirror
ou	Outlet
op	Optical
s	Solar

t	Total or stagnation variable, tube
tr	Tracking
u	Useful
w	Wall

Superscripts

cal	Calculated value
dy	Dynamic
exp	Experimental value
min	Minimum
max	Maximum
st	Steady-state, static

Acronyms

HTF	Heat Transfer Fluid
IAM	Incident Angle Modifier
LFC	Linear Fresnel Collector
OA	Open to Atmosphere
PTC	Parabolic Trough Collector
SAH	Solar Air Heater
T-SAH	Turbo-assisted Solar Air Heater
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
SHIP	Solar Heat for Industrial Processes

Others

$\langle \rangle$	Functional dependence
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8 Appendix

Well-known equations from [26] are used for determining sun position. True Solar Time is obtained from Local standard time LST through Eqs. (A.2-A.4). Eqs. (A.5) and (A.6) determines solar hour angle ω_s and the incident solar angle θ_z . Solar elevation α_s and azimuth γ_s are computed from Eq. (A.7) and Eq. (A.8).

$$\delta = 23.45 \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{365}\right) (284 + n_d) \quad (\text{A.1})$$

$$E = 229.18(0.000075 + 0.001868 \cos(B) - 0.032077 \sin(B) - 0.014615 \cos(2B) - 0.04089 \sin(2B)) \quad (\text{A.2})$$

$$B = \frac{(n_d - 1)2\pi}{365} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$TST = 4(\lambda_{st} - \lambda_{loc}) + E + LST; \lambda_{st} = -UTC \cdot \frac{2\pi}{24} \quad (A.4)$$

$$\omega_s = \frac{2\pi}{24}(TST - 12 \text{ hr}) \quad (A.5)$$

$$\theta_z = \cos^{-1}[\cos(\Phi_{loc}) \cos(\delta) \cos(\omega_s) + \sin(\Phi_{loc}) \sin(\delta)] \quad (A.6)$$

$$\alpha_s = \frac{\pi}{2} - \theta_z \quad (A.7)$$

$$\gamma_s = \text{sign}(\omega_s) \left| \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{(\sin(\Phi_{loc}) \cos(\theta_z) - \sin(\delta))}{\sin(\theta_z) \cos(\Phi_{loc})} \right) \right| \quad (A.8)$$

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